

delayed heading. The prolonged growth period after hispa infestation significantly improved seed setting in late variety Kajalkalma, but reduced seed setting in Ratna (early) and Mahsuri (medium). In Kajalkalma, early depression of vegetative growth in hispa-infested plots favored effective tiller formation. The delay in heading favored assimilation and accumulation of reserves, promoting reproductive development and grain yield. □

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) damage in Pakistan

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In 1986, WBPH severely damaged rice in Sind and Baluchistan. Crop loss was 70% at some locations. We evaluated 2 varieties in the National Uniform Rice Yield Trial at Usta Muhammad, Nasirabad, Baluchistan. Damage ratings ranged from 5 to 9 (0 = healthy, 9 = dead). Basmati 370 scored a damage rating of 5 (see table). □

Reaction of rice cultivars to WBPH in Baluchistan, Pakistan, 1986.

Cultivar	Damage rating (0 to 9 scale)
BAS 370	5
DR37	6
DR39	6
DR41	6
DR82	6
DM16-5-1	6
IR6-93	6
K17-BLK-4-1 IR2053	7
IR6-104	7
DR36	7
DR42	8
DR83	8
IR6	8
BAS385	8
DR38	8
KS282	9
DR40	9
DR43	9
Lateefy	9

Field evaluation of rice culture resistance to leaffolder (LF) and sheath rot (ShR)

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To select high-yielding cultivars with resistance to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guente and to ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw.) Gem., 64 rice accessions were screened in the field during 1985-86 samba season at Tirur. Seedlings were transplanted, at 25 d after sowing, in 3 rows of 10-m length with 20- × 10-cm spacing. Susceptible check CO 43 was planted after every 10 test entries and on all the 4 sides of the trial field. Plots were fertilized with 125-50-50 kg NPK/ha. All the P and K and 50 kg N were applied basally; the remaining N was topdressed in equal splits at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting. No plant protection measures were given. LF damage incidence was assessed at growth stage 6 and ShR incidence at growth stage 8, using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

LF damage ranged from 5.3 to 95.5% and ShR incidence from 0.8 to 81.1%. Of the 64 entries screened, 13 were resistant, 14 intermediate and 37

Reaction of rices to leaffolder and sheath rot. Samba 1985-86, Rice Research Station, Tirur, India.

Entry	Damage rating	
	Leaffolder	Sheath rot
DPI 1091/5	1	1
White Ponni	1	3
TNAU 80030	1	3
TNAU 80042	3	3
TM 4300	3	3
TM 8381	3	3
AU 42/1	3	3
P 837	3	3
ACM1	3	3
AD 85002	3	3
TM 10232	3	3
TKM 1	3	3
Ponni	3	3
TNAU 654012	5	3
TNAU 831175	5	3
TM 1143	3	5
TM 10137	3	5
Paiyur 1	3	5
BG 367-3	3	5
TM 10265	3	5
IET 7303	5	5
IR 20	5	5
TM 8300	5	5
AD 85004	5	5
IR 42	5	5
TM 1087	5	5
IET 5656	5	5

susceptible to both LF and ShR (see table).

LF infestation and ShR incidence correlated positively. A culture or variety resistant to LF was also resistant to ShR. □

Reaction of rice varieties to thrips

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An unusual dry spell, low rainfall, and high temperature during wet season 1986 caused heavy thrips *Baliothrips biformis* damage in the nursery as well as in the transplanted crop at Ambasamudram. Pest damage was most severe in Aug with 35 °C temperatures that were highly conducive to thrips multiplication.

We scored the reaction to thrips of

81 rice varieties being raised in the preliminary variety trial. The trial in a simple lattice design was replicated twice with spacing 15 cm between rows and 10 cm between plants. Cross plot size was 4 m². The crop was at heading.

Reaction to thrips was scored on leaf damage by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale 1-9.

Only AS13744, RAU4071-57-13, and RP2430-103-56-51 scored 1. Nom scored 9, but 47 scored 3, 25 scored 5 and 6 scored 7. Popular varieties BG367-4, ASD16, and IR64 scored 5. □